

Bridging the gap between electronics and nanotechnology

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Abstract—Over the last decades the unprecedented evolution in material science has fueled the development of new nanodevices capable of supporting the development of new circuits and systems operating at higher frequency ranges and with reduced power consumption. However, the development of new nanodevices is supported by material science professionals while electronic engineers are responsible for the implementation of circuits/systems integrating these devices. At the academic level, there is an urgent need for graduating professionals capable of bridging the gap between the design of the nanodevices and their integration into circuits capable of taking advantages of the devices characteristics to keep pushing forward the circuits/systems performances.

Keywords—nanodevices, flexible devices, transparent electronics

I. INTRODUCTION

During the last decades the evolution of nanotechnologies yielded the development of new devices enabling the implementation of electronic equipment operating at higher frequencies, while consuming less power and with smaller form factors. In the last decades, the development of circuits operating at higher frequencies has been made possible through the adoption of new solutions for nano scale MOSFETS. In particular, new materials have been adopted for the gate electrode (e.g., polysilicon heavily doped, TiN and TaN), the oxide was replaced with high-K dielectrics and new materials (e.g. strained silicon SiGe, Ge, InGaAsilicon) were used for the channel as a way of increasing the carriers' mobility. Also, the transistor structure was initially improved from Bulk MOSFET to SOI and later from planar to vertical multiple-gate devices like FinFET, Triple Gate and Gate all around devices as a way of mitigating the short channel effects arising from the quantum mechanical tunneling of carriers both through the thin gate oxide as well as from source to drain and from drain to body [1]. Alternatives to conventional CMOS transistors have also been proposed, such as Tunnel-FET (TFET) devices [2].

Concomitantly, the development of new materials, as well as new manufacturing approaches, have made possible the implementation new devices such as sensors, actuators, circuits and other electronic devices on flexible and stretchable substrates, yielding the possibility to develop integrated multifunctional devices capable extending their applicability to

a plethora of new application areas such as soft robotics, artificial muscles or flexible wearable devices [3], [4]. In particular, thin film transistors (TFT) are becoming a perfect candidate for many innovative applications [5] (e.g., flexible and wearable electronics [6][7]) since they may show a wide range of electrical and mechanical characteristics due to their possibility to be made of a diversified set of materials. Moreover, the potential of processing thin film transistors on larger substrates at a lower cost per unit area, make them suitable for implementing the backplane transistor array for micro led displays [8].

The evolution of nanoelectronics devices has traditionally been supported by material science engineers. At the initial stages of the new devices design, the evaluation of their electrical behavior is obtained through the development of models capable of predicting the devices performances based on their structure and the multiple materials they are made of. These models consider the underlying physics of the material properties and are usually referred to as TCAD (i.e., technology computer-aided design) Models. Such TCAD models generally solve the physical equations (e.g. Poisson's equation, Schrodinger's equation) numerically based on the finite-element method. These TCAD models are fundamental for the design and optimization of the semiconductor devices. However, the complexity of self-consistently solving these differential equations results in prohibitively long simulation times (from few minutes to few days) which may not be satisfying with consideration to the product design cycle. It is, therefore, crucial to have concise descriptions of the devices complex behavior, i.e. compact models, capable of offering designers the possibility to efficiently obtain the electrical characterization of circuits integrating the new devices. It is to be noted, however, that the development of compact models poses severe constraints, that the professionals need to take into consideration. There is, therefore, a major need for offering electronic engineering students the expertise to develop compact models as a way of bridging the gap between material science and electronics.

In this presentation, the case for a course on EDA tools development will be addressed. The motivations will be discussed where the need to offer students the appropriate skills regarding nanofabrication and characterization tools, as well as to allow them to acquire the necessary knowledge to develop new circuits and applications using nano electronic devices will

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be addressed. Also, some examples of the projects developed by students will be presented. These projects entail the development of the models, the automatic evaluation of the model parameters through optimization techniques, the integration of the models in Cadence environment and, finally their use in more complex circuits.

II. NANOELECTRONICS DESIGN CHALLENGES

During the last decades, the evolution of nanoelectronics has made possible the development of cutting-edge devices with ever reduced size, and capable of integrating systems operating at higher frequencies.

It is to be noted however, that bridging the gap from the development of new devices, until their general use by circuit designers, requires a very lengthy way, making use of dedicated computer aided tools at different abstraction levels, that constitute what is usually denominated by electronic design automation (EDA) environments. At the lower abstraction level, semiconductor engineers use Technology Computer Aided Design (TCAD) tools to predict the devices performances, based on their structure, as well as on the multiple materials they are made of. Existing TCAD tools (e.g. Sentaurus), offer semiconductor engineers the possibility to perform computer simulations to evaluate the devices electrical, thermal, and optical behaviour. Moreover, these tools help researchers to optimize devices for power, performance, and area (PPA), including in the face of process variability that can result in electrical noise.

However, for Integrated Circuit (IC) design engineers, the need for efficiently designing large-scale highly integrated circuits is not compatible with the lengthy simulated times of TCAD simulators. At the IC design level, EDA tools rely on the existence of process design kits (PDK) that support the circuits design flow, from schematic simulation and physical verification till the final post-layout simulation [9]. As illustrated in figure 1, PDKs include a set of technology files containing the definitions for the design rules, as well as the definitions of the devices and the parasitic. Besides the technology files, a file containing the devices compact models (e.g. spice/verilog-A) to be used for the simulation of the circuit is provided.

Fig. 1. Process Design Kit information. Adapted from [9]

Compact models for semiconductor devices (e.g., transistors, memories) constitute a channel to share information between foundries and designers[10]. Compact models comprehend concise analytical expressions capable of reproducing the devices complex behavior, and they are usually implemented specific languages such as VHDL or Verilog-A/AMS. Examples of compact models for Mosfet devices are ACM2[11], BSIM[12], EKV[13] and PSP[14] models. These models are

incorporated into electrical simulators yielding the possibility for designers to perform accurate IC design simulations. In the particular case of Mosfets, the compact models comprise a core with simplified analytical expressions for current-voltage (I-V) and capacitance-voltage (C-V) models, appropriate for long channel devices, as well as several additional physically derived equations for different effects arising in real nanoscale devices.

Besides the above-mentioned well-established models for CMOS devices, other compact models for emerging nano devices, (e.g., Magnetic Tunnel Junction (MTJ) [15], Thin Film Transistors (TFT) [16], Carbon Nanotubes [17], Memristors [11]–[14]) can be found in the literature.

A. Compact Models Development

The process for implementing nanodevices models in Matlab or Python is often a straight-forward procedure, where analytical expressions derived from the characterization of the main physical phenomena responsible for the device behaviour are implemented. Then, for the determination of the model parameters, optimization-based techniques are applied to evaluate the values for the model parameters that will guarantee a best fit between the results obtained with the model and those resulting from experimental data or TCAD simulations. Should there be the need, fitting parameters may be added to the analytical model as a way of guaranteeing a better accuracy and scalability of the results.

The development of a device compact model, however, is a complex task that requires not only advanced programming skills but also a deep understanding of the CAD environment they are to be integrated in, as well as a deep knowledge of the specificities of the programming language (e.g. verilog-A) they are to be implemented in. In particular, besides the need for accurately represent the device behaviour, and not consuming prohibitive computation times, compact models must also satisfy additional restrictive requirements arising from their integration into the numerical procedures within the electrical simulators, as well as from the iterative nature of the simulation processes [22]. Electrical simulators like SPICE use the modified nodal analysis as well as implicit integration techniques based on Newton-Raphson (NR) method to solve the circuit analog equations at each time step [23]. For the compatibility with the NR method, compact model functions should be at least of Class 1 order, although higher orders should be envisaged as a way of achieving faster convergence. Moreover, model equations must produce real finite output results, even for input and internal variables values that are outside the physically admissible limits of the device, as the NR algorithm may need to consider this wider search space while converging for a feasible solution.

Further requirements for compact models should also be considered that stem from the modelling language in which they are to be implemented. A comprehensive description of modelling functions/statements to be avoided when using Verilog A can be found in [24].

Once a compact model is duly implemented, a final question remains to be solved that concerns the model parameters extraction for a given technology. As previously stated, this may be done applying curve-fitting procedures to either results from TCAD simulations or even semiconductor data. For the

evaluation of the model parameters either a fully statistics base or model-based methodology may be considered. In the first case, all the model parameters are obtained at the same time through optimization based fitting procedures. Since the optimization problem is usually non-convex, results obtained may reflect either an absolute minimum (i.e., by using evolutionary algorithms) or even a local minimum where the parameter values obtained are inconsistent with the device behaviour being modelled. To overcome this situation, a model-based methodology that considers the “specific” characteristics/regions of operation of the device may be considered, where some parameters that are “responsible” for the device behavior may be isolated by manipulating the corresponding analytical expressions of the model. In this case, the model parameters are determined in a sequential way, avoiding the hypothesis of the process being trapped in a local minimum (or even an absolute minimum) where results are not consistent with the device being modelled.

III. ELECTRONIC DESIGN AUTOMATION TRAINING

Traditional engineering education, which largely focuses on a particular domain, is no longer sufficient for the new nanotechnology era. It is urgent to offer students the training for them to be able to adapt to the quick evolution of nano- devices. Future professionals need the skills to be able to establish the link between semiconductor fabrication and circuit implementation. In particular, students must not only be aware of the limitations of the traditional quadratic model for devices (e.g. Mosfets) in deep submicron/ nano scale, but they need to acquire competences that makes them capable of using new nano devices in their circuit implementations. It is therefore fundamental to offer students skills on device modelling, parameter extraction, implementation of compact models and subsequent integration into electrical simulators.

To this end, the major concern is offering graduates the possibility for developing projects integrating semiconductor knowledge in nanofabrication, which is traditionally offered in nanotechnology courses, with circuit level design that is traditionally addressed in electronics courses. In the next subsections, examples of projects that fulfil the envisioned requirements, by addressing an emerging area of nano devices are presented. The first project concerns the integration into Cadence of a simple *TFT* model for *DC* simulations. In the last example the integration into cadence of a micro-led verilog-A model and subsequent behaviour evaluation of the a micro-led display cell through electrical simulation is addressed.

A. *TFT Model Implementation*

This project considered the evaluation of the model parameters for thin film transistors and integration of the corresponding verilog-A DC model into cadence environment.

1) *TFT Modeling*

The first part of the project aimed the implementation of a verilog model for the DC characterization of *TFTs*, considering experimental values previously obtained. The drain current is

considered null for gate to source voltages below a threshold value (i.e., V_T) and otherwise given by [16]:

$$I_D = \begin{cases} \frac{WC_i}{L_{eff}} \mu_{eff} \left(V_{GS} - V_T - \frac{V_{DS}}{2\alpha} \right) V_{DS} & V_{DS} < V_{DSAT} \\ \frac{WC_i}{2L_{eff}} \mu_{eff} \alpha (V_{GS} - V_T)^2 & V_{DS} \geq V_{DSAT} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

With:

$$V_{DSAT} = \alpha (V_{GS} - V_T), \quad (2)$$

where α is a fitting parameter, and the effective mobility μ_{eff} is evaluated with

$$\mu_{eff} = \mu_0 \frac{(V_{GS} - V_T)^\gamma}{V_{AA}}. \quad (3)$$

2) *TFT Parameter Extraction Methodology*

A model-oriented methodology was considered where the parameters are evaluated in a sequential way, where analytical expressions of the device model are manipulated in a way that allows isolating some of its parameters. The methodology for the determination of the model parameters starts by considering the experimental data from the DC transfer characteristic of the device. Using (1) and (3) we may rewrite the analytical expression for the drain current in saturation as

$$I_{Dsat} = K (V_{GS} - V_T)^m, \quad (4)$$

where,

$$K = \frac{W}{2L_{eff}} \frac{\mu_0}{V_{AA}^\gamma} C_i \alpha, \quad (5)$$

and

$$m = 2 + \gamma. \quad (6)$$

Using (4), it is possible to obtain an analytical expression independent of the parameters K and α , through

$$\frac{I_{Dsat}}{gm} = \frac{(V_{GS} - V_T)}{m}. \quad (7)$$

The first step in the proposed methodology, considers evaluating the numerical differentiation of *TFT* transfer characteristic to obtain a vector of values for the transconductance gm , deriving a vector with values for I_{Dsat}/gm and then, fitting it to (7) as a way of obtaining values for the threshold voltage V_t , and the power parameter m . Next, the values for V_t and m are considered in (4) and fitted to the experimental transfer characteristic allowing the determination of the parameter K value. Finally, from (1) and (4), we may conclude that the analytical expression for the drain current may be written as:

$$I_{DS} = \begin{cases} \frac{K V_{ovd}^{m-2}}{0.5 \alpha} \cdot \left(V_{ovd} - \frac{V_{DS}}{2\alpha} \right) \cdot V_{DS}, & V_{DS} < V_{DSAT}, \\ K V_{ovd}^m V_{DS} \cdot \alpha & V_{DS} \geq V_{DSAT}, \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

given that

$$V_{ovd} = V_{GS} - V_T. \quad (9)$$

It may therefore be concluded that α may be obtained by feeding the previously determined parameters into (8) and proceeding with the corresponding fitting to the previously obtained experimental device output characteristic.

3) Automatic Parameter Evaluation

A Python script for the automatic evaluation of the *TFT* model parameters, following the methodology presented was developed. The script starts by obtaining the *TFT* characteristics from the files automatically generated from the experimental measurements on implemented amorphous indium-gallium-zinc oxide thin-film transistor. Then, from the device transfer characteristic the corresponding differential conductance, g_m is numerically evaluated, the characteristic I_{DS}/g_m is generated, and parameters are obtained through fitting to (7).

The python code used for obtaining V_t and m is represented in List.1, where the analytical expression for I_{DS}/g_m is given by (8) for $V_{GS} \geq V_T$ and it is considered as null for $V_{GS} < V_T$.

```
#Evaluate Vt and m
def dydx(y,x):
    return np.diff(y)/np.diff(x)
def get_vt_m(vg,vt,m):
    return np.piecewise(vg,
    [vg <= vt, vg>vt],
    [lambda vg: 0,
    lambda vg: (vg-vt)/m])
gm= dydx(ID_sat, VG_sat)
ID_of_gm= ID_sat[1:]/gm
[Vt,m],xy=curve_fit(get_vt_m,VG_sat[1:],ID_of_gm)
```

List 1. Python code for evaluating parameters V_T and m

Next parameter K is evaluated. Since the analytical expression for the drain current, (4), is only valid for voltages above the threshold value, the fitting process is applied only for gate voltages corresponding to this region, as duly illustrated in the python code represented in List 2.

```
VG_i=np.where(VG_sat>Vt)[0]
init=VG_i[0]
def get_Ix(vg,vt,m):
    return np.piecewise(vg,
    [vg <= vt, vg>vt],
    [lambda vg: 0,
    lambda vg: (vg-vt)**m])
def get_K(Izx,kx):
    return Izx*kx
Ix=get_Ix(VG_sat,Vt,m)
[K],yK=curve_fit(get_K,Ix[init:],ID_sat[init:])
```

List 2. Python code for evaluating parameter K

Finally, the output characteristic of the device is fitted against the model (8) and parameter α is obtained, as illustrated in List 3

```
vg=7
def get_alfa(vds,alfa):
    vdsat=alfa*(vg-Vt)
    return np.piecewise(vds, [vds <= vdsat, vds>vdsat],
    [lambda vds: (2*K/alfa)*(vg-Vt)**(m-2)*vds*(vg-Vt-
    0.5*vds/alfa),
    lambda vds: K*(vg-Vt)**m])
[alfa],yK=curve_fit(get_alfa,Vdo_7,Ido_7,bounds=(0.0,3))
```

List 3: Python code for evaluating parameter α

4) Working Example

The proposed methodology was applied to the determination of the model parameter for a thin film transistor with $W/L=50/05$ [$\mu\text{m}/\mu\text{m}$]. In figure 2 the behavior I_{DS}/g_m is depicted, as well as the results analytically obtained with the obtained values for V_t and m through the fitting process to (8).

Fig. 2. I_D/g_m characteristics

It is to be noted, that for very small values of the gate voltage, a high dispersion of values for the characteristic is observed. This is due to the difficulty of obtaining a high accuracy in the measurements for the drain current in this range of voltages. This fact, however, does not constitute a severe limitation for the evaluation of V_t and m , since these parameters affect a model that is valid only for gate voltages above V_t . Moreover, most of the characteristic points belonging to this last-mentioned region, show a behavior consistent with what is expected. The model parameters obtained with the methodology proposed are presented in in Table I,

Table 1:TFT Model Parameters

V_t	γ	K	α
-1.29	0.63	1.546e-06	1.047

The *TFT* transfer characteristic obtained with (4) is compared against experimental results and represented in figure 3. In the same figure this comparison is also presented in logarithmic scale, illustrating the high accuracy of the results obtained.

Fig. 3. TFT transfer characteristic for $V_D=7.0$ V

Finally, the output characteristic obtained with (8) and the experimental results are illustrated in figure 4, showing the very acceptable accuracy of the results evaluated.

Fig. 4. TFT output characteristic for $V_G=7.0$ V

B. Micro-led display project

Micro-light-emitting diodes (micro-leds) are becoming a most promising candidate for next generation display technologies due to their superior characteristics in terms of ultrahigh luminance, resolution, efficiency, as well as long lifespan, when compared to today liquid crystal (*LCD*) or organic light-emitting displays (*OLED*) [25], [26]. Micro-leds are mostly often associated to their use in the next generation display technology [27], although their use in optical communications is also gaining increasing relevance [28], [29].

This project concerns the study of a display cell with 2T1C pixel display cell architecture represented in figure 5 [30], in two phases entailing the implementation of the micro-cell model, and the electrical stimulation of the overall display cell.

Fig. 5. 2T1C display cell architecture

1) Micro-led modeling

From the electronic engineering point of view, the need for electrically simulating the micro-led with the *TFT* backplane

relies on the availability of micro-led compact model (e.g., verilog-A model) in the simulation environment.

For the implementation of micro-led verilog-A model, experimental data resulting from measurements of the current voltage characteristic of the device must be obtained. Then, once an analytical model is chosen, the determination of the model parameters through optimization-based techniques is performed. Finally, the obtained model is developed in verilog-A and duly integrated into the electrical simulation environment.

a) Working Example

The graphical representation of the experimental current voltage characteristic obtained for a $25\mu \times 65\mu$ micro-led is illustrated in figure 6, where a current compliance value of $3\mu A$ was established.

Fig. 6. Experimental micro-led current voltage characteristic

As can be easily concluded, the adoption of an analytical model that is capable of accurately reproducing the experimental results for all the values of the controlling voltage and that follows the needed specificities to be integrated into an electrical simulator (i.e., C1) is not easily obtained.

Since the micro-led is to be used for currents between 10 nA and $3\mu A$, the analytical model to be developed, should accurately represent the micro-led characteristic for the control voltages corresponding to current values below its compliance value, as represented in figure 7.

Fig. 7. Micro-led $I(V)$ for current values of interest

From the current-voltage characteristic represented in logarithmic scale it can be easily concluded that the model should follow an exponential behavior. Consequently, the models represented in

Table 2, where U_T is the thermal voltage, were considered.

Table 2: Micro-led models

Model	I(V)	Parameters			
1	$I = I_s \left(e^{\frac{(V-vt)}{U_T}} - 1 \right)$	Is	Vt		
2	$I = I_s \left(e^{\frac{(V-vt)}{n.U_T}} - 1 \right)$	Is	Vt	n	
3	$I = I_s \left(e^{\frac{(V-vt-Rs.I)}{n.U_T}} - 1 \right)$	Is	Vt	n	Rs

A python script was developed for obtaining the model parameters through curve-fitting to the experimental results, represented in figure 7. The parameters obtained, considering a temperature of 300K are represented in Table 3.

Table 3: Model Parameters

Model	Is [A]	Vt [V]	n	Rs [Ω]
1	9.443e-19	1.438		
2	2.842e-13	1.631	1.326	
3	1.369e-13	1.689	1.114	3644.63

For each of the models, the current voltage characteristic, obtained with the evaluated parameters, was compared to the experimental results, as represented in figure 8.

Fig. 8. Current Voltage characteristics obtained with the models proposed.

From the relative error between results obtained with the proposed models and the experimental values, illustrated in figure 9, model 2 was chosen and implemented in Verilog-A

Fig. 9. Micro-led models' relative errors

The Verilog-A code implemented is represented in List.3

```
// Verilog-A for microled
`include "constants.vams"
`include "disciplines.vams"
module microled_exp_lin(p1,p2);
inout p1,p2;
electrical p1,p2;
parameter real Is=2.824e-13;
parameter real Imax=3e-6;
parameter real n=1.326;
parameter real ut=0.026;
parameter real vt0=1.631;
real vg,vg_max,ni;

function my_exp;
input vg, vmax,vtx,nfi;
real vg,vmax,vtx,nfi,ex;
begin
if(vg <= vmax)
my_ex=exp((vg-vtx)/nfi);
else
my_ex=exp((vmax-vtx)/nfi)*(1+(vg-vmax)/nfi);
end
endfunction

analog begin
vg=V(p1,p2);
ni=n*ut;
vg_max=ni*ln(1+Imax/Is)+vt0;
I(p1,p2)<+ Is*(my_exp(vg,vg_max,vt0,ni)-1);
end
endmodule
```

List. 3 Verilog-A code for the micro-led model

It is to be noted that to avoid convergence problems during simulation, the exponential function was replaced by an approximate function (i.e., my_exp) that shows an exponential behavior for the current values of interest, whereas a linear behavior is adopted for current values above the corresponding compliance value. The comparison between the results with verilog-A model and experimental data are illustrated in **Error! Reference source not found. 10**, demonstrating the validity of model developed.

Fig. 10. Micro-led current-voltage characteristic from the verilog-A model

2) Display Cell behavior

The display cell represented in figure 5 was simulated in Cadence using Pragmatic 60nm PDK for the transistors modeling, and the developed verilog-A model for the micro-led. The determination of the transistor sizes was performed considering a supply voltage of $V_{DD}=3.0V$. Since the micro-led starts to light up at 1.96 V, a $V_{S1} = 2.0 V$ was considered leading to $V_{DS1} = 1.0 V$. Finally, considering $0 \leq V_{sel} \leq 3.0$ leads to $0 \leq V_{GS1} \leq 1.0$. The transistor sizes obtained are represented in table 4.

Table 4: 2T1C transistor sizes

Transistor	W	L
T1	4 μm	0.6 μm
T2	2 μm	0.6 μm

The simulated transfer characteristic of T1 for $V_{DS} = 1.0 V$ represented in figure 11 confirms the ability of the device to feed the current needed for the micro-led.

Fig. 11. Driver transfer characteristic

Moreover, the simulated output characteristics of the transistor, for the envisaged range of gate to source voltages demonstrates that the device will keep working in the saturation regime, as illustrated in figure 12.

Fig. 12. Driver Output characteristics

Finally, the switching behavior of the 2T1C display cell with a capacitance of 2pF was evaluated through a transient simulation.

Fig. 13. 2T1C transient simulation results

The results illustrated in **Error! Reference source not found**. 13, consider a refresh rate of 60 Hz ($T_{frame} \approx 16.67$ ms), and 5x5 Pixel resolution ($T_{line} \approx 3.33$ ms). Also, a maximum error of 16% is observed for $V_{data} = 0.5 V$, whereas the error for $V_{data} \geq 1.96$ is less than 5%.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The rapid evolution of nanotechnologies yielded the development of new devices enabling the implementation of electronic equipment operating at higher frequencies, while consuming less power and with smaller form factors. The development of the new nano devices is supported by TCAD simulators using models capable of predicting the devices performances based on their structure and the multiple materials they are made of. However, for Integrated Circuit (IC) design engineers, the need for efficiently designing large-scale highly integrated circuits is not compatible with the lengthy simulated times of TCAD simulators. At the IC design level, EDA tools relying on the existence of process design kits (PDK) that support the circuits design flow, from schematic simulation and physical verification till the final post-layout simulation must be used [9]. To cope with the nano devices' technological evolution, professionals capable of developing compact models are needed. Therefore, there is an urgency for offering graduates the opportunity to acquire the training needed for them to acquire the knowledge and skills to develop the tools needed for establishing the link between semiconductor and IC design proficiency. This paper illustrated the case for two projects developed by master students at an EDA development curricular unit that envisages offering them an initial training at the border between semiconductor knowledge and IC design.

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